

Exploration of Cyber Ethics among Research Scholar

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Abstract:

In present digital scenario the significance of cyber ethics increasing day-by day. Specially in higher education. Cyber ethics are set of rules that govern online behaviour. This study is based on exploration of cyber ethics among research scholars. This research explores how researcher mention discipline when they are on computer and internet. In this Study the researcher used descriptive survey method and data collected through stratified random sampling with the help of self-made questionnaire from 39 research scholars of the Department of Education University of Lucknow. After analysing the data findings of the study revealed that the scholars of university are highly aware about cyber ethics.

Keywords: Cyber Ethics, Ethical use, privacy, awareness, code of ethics.

Introduction:

The revolution of digitization in field of education has opened new dimensions. These are incredibly increasing opportunities like flexibility, equity, accessibility anytime, anywhere for scholars. Scholars do their research with the help of technology. Technology help to researcher to connect worlds experts, researcher in the area of his research. Basically, it is best for scholars . But the more use of technology raises many cyber ethical issues. Cyber ethics is a code of conduct for scholars when they use the internet. They should not access, use or share personal information of others without consent, research scholar should always protect their digital identity and data, research scholars should not plagiarize, cheat or falsify information online. Research scholars should engage in respectful communication online. They are avoiding cyber bullying harassment, trolling or spreading rumours , there should be the code of ethics and morality building in research scholars so they are well aware. Cyber ethics are moral principles, good or bad, write and wrong behaviour, rules and regulations when scholars are in the digital sphere. These included online privacy, digital citizenship and ethical use of resources.

Online privacy refers to the protection of scholar's personal data and activities when they use the internet like escape to use unofficial websites, secure cookies, use only These websites those who https: secure. Escapes to use unsecured wi-fi and so more. Digital citizenship refers to the responsible, respectful and ethical use of technology by scholars when they are in a digital environment, internet and social media. It is for good, respectful and safe behaviour.

Ethical use of online resources is about digital content like image, video, software in ways to use fair, honest and respectful other things. It includes using online content by properly quoting and with the permission of the author.

Understanding and practicing cyber ethics is a matter not only for personal concern but also of professional relevance for every scholar. Cyber meaning working on computer and computer network. Ethics are code of conduct, characteristics and behaviour. The raising of ethical issues in his research practices creates so many problems. That's why the researcher chose this topic for Exploration of Cyber ethics Awareness among research scholar

Cyber ethical practices in research are concerned with use of networks. Internet awareness about it. In the 1990s, use of the internet was started and with these cyber ethical issues were also raised. That's why cyber ethics catch everyone's attention. (Buthelezi, N.,2024) accessed the cyber ethical behaviour of high school students and found that the students did not seem to be aware of the Cyber Ethics. Training requirement since the school is from this environment and not teaching enough about Cybernetics. cyber ethics implies the rules of social engagement and responsibility on cyber ethics (Santosh. & Thiyagu, K.2024). It is really about socially responsible behaviour in man when using the online environment. Studies like Juan, Cesar and Garcia2023 revealed that many are conscious of unethical practices such as cyber bullying, fraud and hacking. There is a notable lack of collaboration approaches to best practices in computer security and insufficient training on cyber ethical behaviour within these institutions. This study indicates a gap between awareness and practical application of ethical guidelines in the digital environment. Research conducted by Naresh, K.,etal2023 showed that students have a high level of awareness on certain questions like in privacy and trust they are lacking basic knowledge on the aspect of password management, phishing and two factor authentication and also shows there is no active program for rising cyber security knowledge among students. Another study Banerjee & Vaish, 2022 stated that a great need for cyber ethics as various cyber related issues are increasing like spying, fraud, exploitative conduct. Prevention measures to deal with cybercrime related issues should be known by all. Doctoral students are globally accepted as facilitates the searching and retrieval of information needed for these academics and consequently the successful completion of their doctoral programs(Adeyimirin,A.2021). The need to be aware and knowledgeable about the ethics surrounding the use of ICT is therefore important. Pre-service teachers reported relatively similar levels of competency in applying copyright and respecting privacy rules with preservice teachers in Malta and Norway reporting higher degrees of knowledge and awareness than this country parts Spain(Gass,H.H2021).After reviewing the research, the researcher found that there is a need for people aware about Cyber ethics to escape any type of cyber related issues.

Significant of the study

This study is significant for the insight that might be derived to help in raising better future preparedness among scholars in their research this research explores ethical dimensions of digital technologies.

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars of University of Lucknow.
2. To know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars on the basis of gender and region of University of Lucknow.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between the mean score of awareness of Cyber ethics among male and female research scholars of University of Lucknow.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean score of awareness of Cyber ethics among rural and urban research scholars of University of Lucknow.

Delimitations of the Study

1. This study delimits only three dimensions; these are online privacy, digital citizenship, and ethical use of online resources.
2. This study is confined to the city of Lucknow.
3. This study is confined to the research scholars University of Lucknow.

Methodology

Descriptive survey research was conducted to Explore Cyber ethics in Teaching Learning Practices among research scholars of University of Lucknow. Convenient sampling technique was used for sample collection research scholars of University of Lucknow. Data was collected through self-made questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed five-point scale Strongly Disagree 1, Disagree 2, Neutral 3, Agree 4, Strongly Agree 5.

Results and Analysis

Objective:1 To know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars of University of Lucknow.

Table 1.1

Statistic	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Median
Value	4.17	0.43	3.27	5.00	(50%)4.19

Is showing the average score of $M=4.17$ indicates a high level of awareness of cyber ethics among research scholars. The narrow spread ($SD=0.43$) suggests consistent understanding across the sample, and the majority of responses leaned towards agreements or strong agreement with ethical statement.

Objective:2 To know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars on the basis of gender and region of University of Lucknow.

Table 1.2:Ranks

	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Rank
AWARENESS MALE	14	21.32	298.50
FEMALE	25	19.26	481.50
Total	39		

Table 1.3 :Test Statistics

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
AWARENESS	156.50	481.50	-. 54	. 588

Awareness by Gender

The result of Mann-Whitney U test in respect of objective, namely, to the level of awareness among male and female scholars should be interpreted as given below:

The objective was to know To know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars. The data were analysed with the help of Mann Whitney U test. The result is given in below table

Table 1.4: Gender-wise Mean Ranks, N and Mann Whitney U value of Awareness

GENDER	MEAN RANKS	N	Mann Whitney- U value
Male	21.23	14	156.50
Female	19.26	25	

From table 1.4, it can be seen that the Mann-Whitney U value is 156.50 which is not statistically significant difference in awareness scores between males (Mean Rank = 21.32, n = 14) and females (Mean Rank = 19.26, n = 25), $U = 156.50$, $Z = -0.54$, $p = .588$ (two-tailed). Thus, the null hypothesis There is no significant difference between the mean score of awareness of Cyber ethics among male and female research scholars of University of Lucknow is not rejected. It may therefore, be said that gender does not significantly influence awareness levels in this sample.

Table 1.5

	N	Mean Ranks	Sum of Ranks
Awareness Urban	23	19.83	456.003
Rural	16	20.25	24.00
Total	39		

Table 1.6 : Test Statistics

	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
AWARENESS	180.00	456.00	-.11	.909

Awareness by Region

The result of Mann-Whitney U test in respect of objective, namely, to the level of awareness among urban and rural scholars should be interpreted as given below:

The objective was to know the level of awareness of Cyber ethics among research scholars. The data were analysed with the help of Mann Whitney U test. The result is given in table.

Table 1.7: Region-wise Mean Ranks, N and Mann Whitney U value of Awareness

Region	MEAN RANKS	N	Mann Whitney-U value
Urban	19.83	23	180.00
Rural	20.25	16	

From table 1.7, it can be seen that the Mann-Whitney U value is 180.00 which is not statistically significant difference in awareness scores between urban and rural areas (Mean Rank = 19.83, n = 23) and those from rural areas (Mean Rank = 20.25, n = 16), U = 180.00, Z = -0.11, p = .909 (two-tailed). Thus, the null hypothesis There is no significant difference between the mean score of awareness of Cyber ethics among male and female research scholars of University of Lucknow is accepted. It may therefore, be said that gender does not significantly influence awareness levels in this sample.

Discussion and suggestion:

In this study the findings of the research is show after result awareness of cyber ethics is high among research scholars. There is no significant differences were found based on gender or region. Banerjee & Vaish, 2022 stated that a great need for cyber ethics as various cyber related issues . This study implies that awareness programs and digital ethics policies are being equally absorbed across demographic in the university. This is good for researchers’ future and perspective. Researcher follow quality researches and maintain research standards. Cyber ethics education encourages safe internet use, respect for privacy, and data protection. Awareness level can inform national or institutional policies in digital education. Schools and University must include cyber ethics in curriculum for teaching students.

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